

Consumer credit card ownership and usage practices: Empirical evidence from Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Knowledge that has been accumulated through research efforts concerning credit card ownership and usage behaviour has been confined to Western societies. Given the importance of cross-national application of consumer marketing concepts and propositions for academic and practical reasons, investigations are needed to test whether consumer credit card usage patterns that are assumed to exist in the West also exist in non-Western parts of the world, especially in Asia. Therefore, objectives of this research were to explore credit card ownership and usage practices in Sri Lanka; and to explore the relationship between credit card ownership and usage practices and demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users. The findings offer implications for researchers and practitioners.

Key words: Consumer, Credit cards, credit card ownership, credit card usage, Sri Lanka.

Introduction

Credit cards have become a vital component of personal money management and consumer lifestyle management (Garcia, 1980; Feinberg, 1986; Holt, 1997; Durkin, 2000; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005). Credit card ownership and use have increased substantially over the past decades and credit card service has become one of the most lucrative financial services (Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Goyal, 2006). Literature provides evidence of the availability of credit cards to working and middle class families as credit card lenders have extended credit to riskier customers (Littwin, 2008). Despite the substantial risks to lenders that they will be unable to pay their bills on time, working and middle class families often pay high rates of interest as they are among the industry's most profitable customers. The high interest rates and penalties can quickly multiply the original

debt, so that a modest number of purchases can leave consumers deeply mired in debt (Littwin, 2008). On the other hand, this broadened access to credit cards facilitates those who are in the working and middle classes to achieve a level of participation in contemporary consumer culture that is qualitatively different from what would be possible in their absence. In this context, the entire range of practices consumers employ to manage their lifestyles with credit cards should be of particular interest to consumer researchers.

Though as a basic marketing rule credit card lenders should be knowledgeable of attitudes of their customers towards credit cards and how they come to use or abuse credit cards (Feinberg, 1986; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), the knowledge that has been accumulated through research efforts concerning credit card ownership and usage behaviour were confined to Western societies (e.g. Slocum and Mathews, 1970; Plummer, 1971; Awh and Waters, 1974; Burman, 1974; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005). Given the importance of cross-national application of consumer marketing concepts and propositions for academic and practical reasons, investigations are needed to test whether consumer attitudes towards credit cards that are assumed to exist in the West also exist in non-Western parts of the world, especially in Asia. Though a few empirical research studies have been conducted on this topic in the developing countries (Barker *et al.*, 1992; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Goyal, 2006), a full array of consumer attitudes towards possession, utilization, the repayment of credit card debt and lifestyle outcomes, and the influence of demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users on these aspects remained virtually unexplored. Therefore, this research undertaken in Sri Lanka is unique in its approach because no previous research has attempted to analyse the areas addressed in this study in the context of an Asian developing country, where credit card business is a lucrative banking service today. In the above context, the specific objectives of the research were: a) to explore credit card ownership and usage practices in Sri Lanka, and b) to explore the relationship between credit card ownership and usage practices and demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users.

In order to provide the context for the article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

According to consumer behaviour literature, consumer usage behaviour and benefits sought from a product or a service are one of the best predictors to explain consumer purchase behaviour (Lee and Kwon, 2002). Consumers use credit cards, which are issued by financial institutions, as a payment device and a source of revolving credit (Garcia, 1980; Hirschman, 1981; Ausubel, 1991; Lee and Hogarth, 1999; Stavins, 2000; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005). Based on the main use of credit cards and benefits sought, extant literature segments credit card users into two groups as convenience users and revolvers (Lee and Hogarth, 1999).

Convenience users tend to use credit cards as an easy mode of payment and to typically pay their balance in full upon receiving the account statement. Revolvers, on the other hand, use the card principally as a mode of financing and elect to pay interest charges on the unpaid balance (Lee and Kwon, 2002). When consumers use credit cards as a mode of financing, credit cards compete with bank loans and other forms of financing (Brito and Hartley, 1995). As a result, credit cards account for a substantial and growing share of consumers' debt through incremental borrowing (Wasberg *et al.*, 1992; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005; Canner and Lockett, 1992; Littwin, 2008).

In the above context, credit cards have raised concerns in two areas, namely, whether consumers fully understand the costs and implications of using credit cards, and whether credit cards have encouraged widespread over indebtedness, particularly among those least able to pay. These two issues are identified as related because the lack of understanding

may result in over indebtedness (Durkin, 2000). Hence, an individual's level of intellectual understanding and comprehension of credit cards and their use, knowledge of and ability to compare information on credit card costs, and literacy on personal finance have become very important (Feinberg, 1986; Mitchell, 1989; d'Astous and Miquelon, 1991; Berlin and Mester, 2004; Kim *et al.*, 2005), especially, in a time period where credit cards have been aggressively marketed and sold, and where credit card issuers have penetrated different demographic and socio-economic markets by relaxing eligibility standard and requirements.

Extant literature identify credit card practices as the reasons for owning credit cards, number of credit cards owned, types of credit card purchases, place of purchase, frequency of usage, payment practices, and all other factors associated with owning and using credit cards (Hirschman, 1979; Feinberg, 1986; Danes and Hira, 1990). Several studies have reported that the demographic and socio-economic background of individuals has a strong influence on their credit card practices (Bearden *et al.*, 1978; Garcia, 1980; Hirschman, 1979; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). Some of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics that have been found to be significant in describing consumer credit card practices are gender, education, income, age, ethnic background, and credit card type (Slocum and Matthews, 1970; Bowers and Crosby, 1980; Chien and DeVaney, 2001; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Lee and Kwon, 2002).

Gender is identified as a significant predictor of credit card ownership and use. Some early studies found that credit card users were more likely to be males (Adcock *et al.*, 1977); single males were more likely to use credit cards than females (White, 1975). Evidence also reveals that the impact of gender on types of credit card purchase is significant, where females use credit cards more for household goods, clothing, and personal belongings (Lindley *et al.*, 1989; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), while males use their cards more for electronics, entertainment, travel, and food away from home (Kaynak *et al.*, 1995; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001).

Extant literature provides evidence for the relationship between the level of education and credit card ownership (Awh and Waters, 1974; Adcock *et al.*, 1977; Canner and Cynrak, 1985; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), and the frequency of credit card usage (Danes and Hira, 1990; Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992) where respondents with a high level of education and knowledge of consumer credit tended to own and use credit cards more often.

Income is another demographic variable that shows a strong positive relationship with credit card ownership and use, where high income groups were found to spend more on different product categories than any other group (Barker and Sekerkaya, 1992; Kaynak *et al.*, 1995; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001). Further, economically less privileged persons use credit cards as a means of instalment credit as they are not able to borrow money from banks at a reasonable rate (Garcia, 1980; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001; Bernthal *et al.*, 2005).

Age is also identified as a significant predictor of credit card ownership and use. Barker and Sekerkaya (1993) and Kaynak and Harcar (2001) suggested that the middle-aged group was more likely to hold and use credit cards. Several researchers in the past have reported a negative impact of age on credit card usage (Awh and Waters, 1974; Adcock, *et al.*, 1977; Wasberg *et al.*, 1992).

Marital status and the number of members in the family are two other demographic characteristics found to influence credit card ownership and use (Delener and Katzenstein, 1994). Married respondents were found to have more credit cards than singles and separated/divorced Asian and Hispanic consumers (Delener and Katzenstein, 1994).

In this Sri Lankan study eight demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users were investigated, namely, age, gender, marital status, the level of education, the number of dependents in the family, monthly income, the length of credit card ownership, and credit card debt ceiling. Based on the empirical and anecdotal evidence indicating the relationship between demographic and socio-economic characteristics of individuals and credit card ownership and use, for this Sri Lankan study, it is proposed that:

H1: Criteria used to evaluate alternative sources of credit cards vary by demographic and socio-economic characteristics of its users.

H2: Types of purchase made with credit cards vary by demographic and socio-economic characteristics of its users.

H3: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users will have a significant impact on consumer awareness of credit cards.

H4: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users will have a significant impact on reasons for obtaining credit cards.

H5: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users will have a significant impact on their attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage.

H6: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users will have a significant impact on their attitudes towards governmental intervention to help consumers make informed choices on competitive credit card offerings.

Measures

The research measures for this study were developed based on the insight gained from the previously reviewed literature that were grounded mainly in the West, and based on the insight gained during the preliminary investigations by the two authors in Sri Lanka. Details of the measures used in the study are as follows.

- Consumer awareness of credit cards- 13 items on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'. Items are shown in Table 2;

- Reasons for obtaining credit cards- 14 items on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'. Items are shown in Table 3;
- Consumer attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage- 13 items on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'. Items are shown in Table 4;
- Criteria used to evaluate alternative sources of credit cards- five criteria were inquired on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'very low' to (5) 'very high'. The five criteria are shown in Table 6;
- Types of purchase made with credit cards- seven types of purchase were inquired on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'always' to (5) 'never'. The seven types of purchase are shown in Table 7 and Table 8;
- The way credit card users generally handle monthly payments on credit cards- five options were provided to circle the most frequently used option. Options are shown in Table 9;
- Consumer attitudes towards governmental intervention to help consumers make informed choices on competitive credit card offerings- one item scale on a five-point Likert scale ranging from (1) 'strongly disagree' to (5) 'strongly agree'.

In addition, questions were asked to collect data on age, gender, marital status, the highest level of education, the number of dependents in the family, monthly income, the length of credit card ownership, debt ceiling, and credit card type. The data provided by respondents were shown in Table 1. These data was thereafter re-coded into two levels as shown in Table 9.

The questionnaire was originally developed in English and then it was translated into native language- *Sinhala*, and finally translated back from *Sinhala* to English. The translated questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of 10 customers that fit with the intended

sample of the study prior to the distribution. It should be noted that this research is conducted as an independent study for academic purposes. Therefore, the questions in the questionnaire were designed by the authors and these did not address specific organizational interests. Further, participants were briefed on the aims of the study prior to data collection and their responses were anonymous. Data was analysed using the SPSS programme. In addition to descriptive statistics, independent sample t-test, factor analysis, correlation and regression were used.

Sample

There is no evidence of studies carried out in Sri Lanka on consumer attitudes towards credit cards. No secondary data sources, such as Consumer Finances, were found to be used in this study. Therefore, the present research study is descriptive in nature conducted purely for academic purposes based on the survey research methodology. The sample of the study is restricted to individuals who possess a credit card issued by a financial institution that allows the cardholder to utilise the card for payments, and as source of revolving credit. There are three types of credit cards in circulation in Sri Lanka, namely VISA, MasterCard, and American Express. The anecdotal information gathered on credit card possession led to suggest that VISA accounts for about 80 per cent of the credit card market, followed by MasterCard (12%), and American Express (8%). Commercial banks operating in the country, primarily, issue these credit cards. A structured questionnaire is used as the research instrument. Questionnaire was administered through face to face personal interviews conducted among a convenience sample of 177 credit card holders employed or self employed in Colombo metropolitan area, which is considered as the main commerce and financial hub of the country, during September and November 2007. All the interviews were conducted by the second author of this study; and the survey took approximately 15 minutes to complete. The demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are

shown in Table 1. Further, income and expenditure data of Sri Lanka are given in Appendix 1.

Table 1 about here

Results

Measure evaluation

In order to establish the dimensionality of the scales, 13 items on consumer awareness of credit cards, 14 items on reasons for obtaining credit cards, and 13 items on consumer attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage were subjected to exploratory factor analysis with direct oblimin rotation, separately. For this, principal components analysis was conducted for the three sets of item scales, separately (suppressed absolute values less than 0.45).

The factor analysis for consumer awareness of credit cards yielded four factors with eigenvalues >1 , which together accounted for 56.55 per cent of the variance. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic was .746 and Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant at .000. The results are shown in Table 2 along with factor loadings, factor variance percentages and Cronbach's alpha of the factor. Person correlation for inter-items and total-items were conducted to identify the relationship across four derived factors. The inter-item correlations were not included in this article due to their excessive length. The total-item correlation results are shown in Table 5, along with other variables investigated in this study. All the 13 items of this scale loaded onto one of the four derived factors, which were consequently labelled as subscales. Factor 1 was labelled as "personal financial literacy", Factor 2 as

“complementary/competitive credit card systems”, Factor 3 as “credit risk” and Factor 4 as “alternative forms of credit”.

Table 2 about here

The factor analysis for reasons for obtaining credit cards yielded four factors with eigenvalues >1, which together accounted for 57.08 per cent of the variance. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic was .779 and Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant at .000. The results are shown in Table 3. All the 14 items of this scale loaded onto one of the four derived factors. Factor 1 was labelled as “transactions convenience”, Factor 2 as “lifestyle facilitator”, Factor 3 as “marketing and communication programmes”, and Factor 4 as “short-term financial support”.

Table 3 about here

The factor analysis for consumer attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage yielded five factors with eigenvalues >1, which together accounted for 64.76 per cent of the variance. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) statistic was .659 and Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant at .000. The results are shown in Table 4. All the 13 items of this scale loaded onto one of the five derived factors. Factor 1 was labelled as “indebtedness”, Factor 2 as “access to mainstream society”, Factor 3 as “enhanced spending”, Factor 4 as “facilitated commerce”, and Factor 5 as “financial confidence”.

Table 4 about here

Table 5 about here

The influence of demographic and socio-economic characteristics on credit card ownership and use

The results of t-test for the criteria used by respondents to evaluate alternative sources of credit cards are shown in Table 6. The influence of age is significant in evaluating credit cards that can be used internationally ($p < 0.01$), where older respondents consider the possibilities of international use. Gender is significant in evaluating debt ceiling ($p < 0.001$), where females pay more attention to debt ceiling than males. The level of education is also significant in evaluating debt ceiling ($p < 0.05$), where highly educated respondents pay more attention to debt ceiling. Further, the level of education is significant in evaluating interest rate ($p < 0.01$), where low educated respondents pay more attention to interest rate. H1 is partially supported.

Table 6 about here

The results of the t-test for the types of purchase made with credit cards are shown in Table 7 and Table 8. The influence of age is significant in making payments for durables, where younger group make more payments for durables than otherwise. Gender is significant in making payments for medical expenses ($p < 0.05$), where females use it more than males. Marital status ($p < 0.01$), the highest level of education ($p < 0.01$), and debt ceiling ($p < 0.05$) are significant in payments for eating out/entertainment, where singles, less educated and credit card holders with low debt ceiling use it for eating out/entertainment than otherwise. The highest level of education ($p < 0.01$) and debt ceiling ($p < 0.01$) are significant in making payments for utility bills and mortgage, where highly educated and credit card holders with

high debt ceiling use more for utility bills and mortgage than otherwise. H2 is partially supported.

Table 7 about here

Table 8 about here

Table 9 shows the results of how respondents generally handle monthly payments on credit cards. 31 percent of the respondents with higher level of education and 25 per cent of respondents with higher credit card debt ceiling tend to pay their balance in full upon receiving the account statement than otherwise. However, over 80 percent of the total respondents and over 74 per cent of respondents across all demographic and socio economic strata tend to make a payment which is greater than or equal to minimum payment due.

Table 9 about here

The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table 10. The four factors of the consumer awareness of credit cards are significant by debt ceiling, marital status, income and the highest level of education. That is, debt ceiling contributed significantly to awareness of personal financial literacy indicating that it could account for 10 per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.102$). Marital status contributed significantly to awareness of complementary/competitive credit card systems indicating that it could account for five per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.047$). Income and debt ceiling contributed significantly to

awareness of credit risk indicating that these two variables could account for seven per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.074$ in model 2, $\Delta R^2: p<0.05$). The highest level of education contributed significantly to awareness of alternative forms of credit indicating that it could account for two per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.022$). Therefore, H3 is partially supported.

Three of the four factors of the reasons for obtaining credit cards are significant by debt ceiling, the length of credit card ownership, and gender. That is, debt ceiling and the length of credit card ownership contributed significantly to transactions convenience and marketing and communication programmes indicating that these two variables could account for 12 per cent of the variance in transactions convenience ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.121$) and seven per cent of the variance in marketing and communication programmes ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.070$ in model 2, $\Delta R^2: p<0.05$), respectively. The length of credit card ownership and gender contributed significantly to short-term financial support indicating that these two variables could account for eight per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.079$ in model 2, $\Delta R^2: p<0.05$). However, lifestyle facilitator, which is one of the factors of reasons for obtaining credit cards, was not predicted by any of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics investigated in the study. Overall, H4 is partially supported.

Four of the five factors of lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage are significant by debt ceiling, gender, income, and marital status. That is, debt ceiling contributed significantly to indebtedness indicating that it could account for six per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.064$). Gender, income and debt ceiling contributed significantly to access to mainstream society indicating that these three variables could account for 18 per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.177$ in model 2, $\Delta R^2: p<0.01$). Marital status contributed significantly to facilitated commerce indicating that it could account for two per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.020$). Gender contributed significantly to financial confidence indicating that it could account for six per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.059$). However, enhanced spending, which is one of the factors of lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, was not

predicted by any of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics investigated in the study. Overall, H5 is partially supported.

Table 10 about here

The result of the consumer attitude towards governmental intervention to help consumers make informed choices on competitive credit card offerings is also shown in Table 10. Debt ceiling and income contributed significantly indicating that these two variables could account for eight per cent of the variance ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}}=0.084$ in model 2, $\Delta R^2: p<0.05$).

Conclusions and implications

The purpose of the current research was to enhance the understanding of consumer credit card ownership and usage practices. We applied quantitative data collection and analysis techniques to capture the dimensions investigated in this study. Further, the study made an attempt to assess the impact of demographic and socio-economic characteristics of credit card users on consumer attitudes towards credit card ownership and usage practices. It could be expected that the findings of this study would lead to the advancement of this area as a field of inquiry as marketing concepts, propositions and research constructs pertaining to credit card ownership and usage behaviour are primarily based on a Western research. Further, the findings could be used to assist credit card lenders to apply strategic decisions in developing and applying marketing strategies, and governmental institutions to help consumers make informed choices on competitive credit card offerings.

It was found that respondents have four broad motives for using credit cards. Credit cards serve as a payment device in lieu of cash for routine purchases as well as for transactions that would otherwise be inconvenient, or perhaps impossible. Further, credit cards help consumers to access a level of participation in contemporary consumer culture that is different from what would be possible in their absence. Furthermore, targeted marketing and communication programmes of credit card lenders also motivate potential customers. Consumers also use credit cards as a mode of short-term financing and realise that savings may result by paying later. Respondents are aware of four broad aspects of credit cards, namely, personal financial literacy, complimentary/competitive credit card systems, credit risk, and alternative forms of credit. Further, respondents' motives for holding credit cards, their awareness of different aspects of credit cards, and the criteria used to evaluate alternative sources of credit cards differ significantly by some of the demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the credit card users.

Respondents' use of credit cards for day-to-day expenses and credit card spending on durables is low. Though previous studies found significant differences in making payments for household goods, clothing, entertainment, travel, and food away from home by gender (see- Lindley *et al.*, 1989; Hayhoe *et al.*, 2000; Kaynak and Harcar, 2001), this study found significant differences only in making payments for medical bills, where females tend to pay medical expenses more than males. The impact of marital status is also significant, where single respondents tend to pay more for eating out/entertainment than married. Further, the level of education is also significant in making payments for utility bills and mortgage and eating out/entertainment, where highly educated respondents spend more on utility bills and mortgage while less educated respondents spend more on eating out/entertainment. Though previous studies indicated that income and the number of dependents in the family influence on the types of purchase (see- Delener and Katzenstein, 1994), the findings of this study did not support those claims. With regard to payment practices, the percentage of respondents who tend to pay their balance in full upon receiving the account statement is low. Exceptions

could only be found in the strata of highly educated and high credit card debt ceiling, where a considerable percentage of those who belong to these two strata settle their bills on time. Overall, the findings suggests that very high percentage of respondents across all demographic and socio-economic strata tend to use credit card as a mode of financing and elect to pay interest charges on outstanding credit card balances. This could result in a growing share of consumers' debt through incremental borrowing.

In connection to the above, the findings suggest five broad lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage, with one of the outcomes being indebtedness. Further, findings suggest that the probability, speed, and magnitude of spending could be enhanced in the presence of credit cards. Hence, a higher level of purchasing expenditure and purchasing item volume could result. The habitual use of credit cards could become an addiction and could lead to difficulties in personal financial practices. This situation could be worsened if individuals tend to spend based on their anticipated future income since most people in general anticipate higher incomes. Consumers also value the symbolism expressed by credit cards that allows them to access mainstream contemporary society. Further, consumers' attitudes towards credit card debt have changed considerably and individuals tend to see credit cards as a convenient and relatively painless way of spending, and that debt has become more socially acceptable. The benefits of facilitated commerce and greater levels of confidence that credit cards provide in spending may influence individuals to accept the dependence on credit cards as an accepted part of everyday life and to approve of them.

Credit cards offer service to customers. This service is a "performance" rather than a "thing". There are more experience and credence qualities with services than search qualities. Further, the experience attributes it has can only be assessed after purchase or during consumption is also high (this sentence needs work – perhaps just remove the last three words?). Therefore, consumers may find difficulties in evaluating credit cards pre-purchase. Hence, choosing an economically appropriate credit card requires knowledge of one's credit card usage and comparison information on credit card costs. However, information about

fees, interest rates, and the methods of calculating interest charges is often incomplete and hard to understand (see- d'Astous and Miquelon, 1991). As information availability is a fundamental component of the free market system, the lack of information about credit cards could be considered as a threat to market competitiveness and to consumer interests. This creates a need for governmental intervention to help consumers compare competitive credit card offerings and the costs of credit cards. Such consumer awareness campaigns would help consumers make informed choices on credit cards and alternative sources of credit. Especially, in a time period where credit cards are aggressively marketed and sold not only to pre-selected groups of individuals, typically in upper income, well educated and highly regarded occupation groups, but also to non-traditional markets, such as students and working and middle class families by relaxing eligibility standard and requirements.

Limitations and future research

The study is confined to a convenience sample of 177 individuals employed/self employed in Colombo metropolitan area. Individuals with one of the three main types of credit cards were taken into account. However, the influence of possessing multiple credit cards by an individual has not been explored. The study had not explored credit history and credit card debt to identify factors influencing the amount of and changes in consumer debt held by households. Though findings suggest that credit cards could result in a higher level of purchasing expenditure and purchasing item volume, it is not clear whether high spenders gravitate toward credit card usage. Hence, cause and effect relationship between credit cards and spending has yet to be adequately explored. Overall, issues involved with possession, utilization, the repayment of credit card debt, lifestyle outcomes are numerous and a single study cannot be expected to address them all. Research is needed to complement the findings.

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Tables

Table 1: Demographic and socio-economic characteristics of the respondents (N=177)

	%		%
The length of ownership:		Age (years):	
Less than 5 years	46	16-25	12
5-10 years	37	26-35	44
More than 10 years	17	36-45	34
		46 or above	10
Card type:		Gender:	
Visa	62	Male	77
MasterCard	34	Female	23
American Express	4		
Debt ceiling (Sri Lankan Rupees):		Marital status:	
Up to 25,000	29	Single	24
Up to 50,000	44	Married	76
Up to 100,000	19		
Above 100,000	8	Highest level of education:	
Number of dependents:		G.C.E. (O/L)*	15
None	14	G.C.E. (A/L)°	68
1	13	Graduate/Postgraduate	17
2	24	Monthly income (Sri Lankan Rupees)†:	
3	36	Less than 15,000	6
4	13	Less than 25,000	20
		Less than 35,000	30
		Less than 45,000	29
		Less than 55,000	9
		Above 55,000	6

Notes:

* General Certificate in Education (Ordinary Level)

° General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level)

† 1 \$US= 108 Sri Lankan Rupees (as at 30th September 2008)

Table 2: Consumer awareness of credit cards

	F1: Personal financial literacy	F2: complementary/ competitive credit card systems	F3: Credit risk	F4: Alternative forms of credit
I am currently managing my credit card debt well	.749			
Even though I have incurred a credit card debt, I am spending money responsibly	.700			
When I decide to incur more credit card debt, I consider my monthly income	.685			
I am successful in living within my budget	.714			
I know ways to reduce my credit card debt	.717			
I am personally responsible for my credit card debt	.607			
I am aware of the different credit card systems on offer		.635		
I am aware of how fees, interest rates, and methods of calculating interest charges by different card issuers		.758		
I am aware of the costs associated with different credit card issuers		.826		
I am aware of the implications of incremental borrowing through credit card without repaying the debt			.579	
I am aware of the implications of getting credit card debt ceiling increased			.578	
I am aware of the implications of borrowing loans/obtaining another credit card to pay my existing credit card debt			.575	
I am aware of the alternative payment and financing methods				.757
Percentage of variance	24.095	16.626	8.165	7.671
Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	.836	.752	.701	--

Table 3: Reasons for obtaining credit cards

	F1: Transactions convenience	F2: Lifestyle facilitator	F3: Marketing & communication programmes	F4: Short-term financial support
Safety and security	.763			
Convenience	.756			
Ease of record keeping as bank regularly deliver bill statements at periodic intervals	.599			
Can be used to cover emergency needs	.675			
My family members' use of credit cards		.508		
To obtain incentives offered on credit cards such as life insurance, bonus tour packages etc.		.556		
To keep up with colleagues and friends		.696		
The policies of the place of purchase regarding acceptable payment systems		.538		
To purchase items through internet		.712		
Prestige		.592		
I was influenced by credit cards promotions			.736	
Advertisements on news paper and TV encouraged me to obtain a credit card			.488	
To delay cash outlay				.880
To help me make ends meet because I often run out of money				.743
Percentage of variance	25.722	14.572	8.745	8.047
Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	.794	.720	.695	.879

Table 4: Consumer attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage

	F1: Indebtedness	F2: Access to mainstream society	F3: Enhanced spending	F4: Facilitated commerce	F5: Financial confidence
Because of credit card debt I have restricted my social activities	.814				
Credit card debt has a negative impact on the harmony of my domestic life	.671				
Credit card has encouraged me to spend beyond my income	.611				
Credit card has placed me in financial difficulties	.693				
The places where I shop have changed and I now purchase things from better places		.814			
Credit card has enabled me to travel more and meet more people		.679			
Credit card has added a quality to my life		.789			
Credit card tempts me to buy things that I do not need			.513		
Credit card has influenced me to spend without carrying monthly balance			.734		
Credit card has encouraged me to spend more and buy more			.729		
Credit card has not influenced my lifestyle to any significant level				.703	
My attitude towards credit cards has changed				.803	
Credit card has boosted my self confidence by enabling me to spend for my needs at any time and any where					.857
Percentage of variance	22.781	14.147	10.525	8.950	8.359
Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	.824	.853	.786	.861	--

Table 6: Criteria used to evaluate alternative sources of credit cards

	Total Mean (N=177)	Age			Gender			Marital status			Education			Monthly income			Dependents		
		35 or less (N=99)	More than 35 (N=78)	Sig (2-tailed)	Male (N=136)	Female (N=41)	Sig (2-tailed)	Single (N=43)	Married (N=134)	Sig (2-tailed)	Low (N=148)	High (N=29)	Sig (2-tailed)	Rs.35,000 or less (N=100)	More than Rs.35, 000 (N=77)	Sig (2-tailed)	2 or less (N=91)	More than 2 (N=86)	Sig (2-tailed)
Brand name	4.12	4.02	4.22	.148	4.06	4.31	.223 [†]	4.16	4.09	.654	4.07	4.33	.176 [†]	4.04	4.18	.283	4.20	4.01	.145 [†]
Interest rate	4.44	4.46	4.39	.648	4.44	4.40	.838	4.50	4.41	.627	4.50	3.92	.006**	4.42	4.42	.884	4.36	4.50	.321 [†]
International use	4.28	3.85	4.52	.014**	4.27	4.30	.938	4.10	4.34	.426	4.29	4.25	.874	4.21	4.35	.605	4.31	4.23	.760
Debt ceiling	3.81	3.86	3.73	.309	3.69	4.22	.000***	3.80	3.81	.997	3.74	4.13	.032*	3.88	3.71	.189	3.91	3.71	.125 [†]
Other benefits	3.61	3.66	3.53	.636	3.54	3.72	.541	3.77	3.54	.452	3.64	3.50	.669	3.76	3.40	.174	3.61	3.60	.969

Notes: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; [†] Normality distribution was violated in running the t-test

Table 7: Types of purchase made with credit cards by age, gender, marital status, and the highest level of education

	Total Mean (N=177)	Age			Gender			Marital status			Education		
		35 or less (N=99)	More than 35 (N=78)	Sig (2-tailed)	Male (N=136)	Female (N=41)	Sig (2-tailed)	Single (N=43)	Married (N=134)	Sig (2-tailed)	Low (N=148)	High (N=29)	Sig (2-tailed)
Food & clothing	4.83	4.81	4.86	.438	4.82	4.87	5.38	4.75	4.85	.311	4.86	4.64	.150 [†]
Medical	3.40	3.38	3.42	.780	3.35	3.66	.080*	3.46	3.38	.630	3.36	3.58	2.33
Utility bills & mortgage	3.68	3.58	3.84	.128	3.65	3.83	.385	3.50	3.74	.217	3.60	4.25	.007**
Travel/vacation	3.86	4.00	3.80	.587	4.00	3.60	.269	3.80	3.90	.787	3.83	3.88	.876
Eating out/entertainment	3.82	3.90	3.71	.151	3.85	3.68	.347	4.14	3.72	.002**	3.90	3.47	.010**
Petrol	3.56	3.54	3.60	.835	3.55	3.60	.894	3.42	3.60	.558	3.55	3.66	.782
Durables	2.26	2.48	1.82	.014**	2.33	2.19	.580	2.31	2.23	.797	2.26	3.33	.871

Notes: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; [†] Normality distribution was violated in running the t-test

Table 8: Types of purchase made with credit cards by monthly income, the length of ownership, and debt ceiling

	Monthly income			Dependents			Length of ownership			Debt ceiling		
	Rs.35,000 or less (N=100)	More than Rs.35, 000 (N=77)	Sig (2-tailed)	2 or less (N=91)	More than 2 (N=86)	Sig (2-tailed)	Less than 5 years (N=82)	5 years or more (N=95)	Sig (2-tailed)	Rs.50,000 or less (N=130)	More than Rs.50, 000 (N=47)	Sig (2-tailed)
Food & clothing	4.81	4.85	.548	4.79	4.87	.297	4.48	4.86	.382	4.85	4.78	.389
Medical	3.38	3.42	.780	3.41	3.40	.967	3.44	3.37	.599	3.33	3.61	.139 [†]
Utility bills & mortgage	3.64	3.76	.472	3.82	3.58	.141	3.65	3.71	.716	3.57	4.06	.010**
Travel/vacation	4.20	3.70	.161	4.00	3.71	.408	4.25	3.72	.361 [†]	4.20	3.70	.161
Eating out/entertainment	3.88	3.75	.317 [†]	3.93	3.71	.106	3.90	3.75	.260 [†]	3.90	3.60	.075*
Petrol	3.55	3.58	.894	3.55	3.57	.948	3.64	3.50	.582 [†]	3.58	3.50	.766
Durables	2.24	2.31	.797	2.27	2.25	.934	2.29	2.24	.823	2.20	2.44	.411

Notes: * p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001; [†] Normality distribution was violated in running the t-test

Table 9: The way users generally handle monthly payments on credit cards (in percentages)

	Total	Age		Gender		Marital status		Education		Monthly income		Dependents		Length of ownership		Debt ceiling	
		35 or less (N=99)	More than 35 (N=78)	Male (N=136)	Female (N=41)	Single (N=43)	Married (N=134)	Low (N=148)	High (N=29)	Rs.35,000 or less (N=100)	More than Rs.35, 000 (N=77)	2 or less (N=91)	More than 2 (N=86)	Less than 5 years (N=82)	5 years or more (N=95)	Rs.50,000 or less (N=130)	More than Rs.50, 000 (N=47)
Payment of total balance no payment due	13.6	12.1	15.4	13.2	14.6	9.3	14.9	10.1	31.0	10.0	18.2	15.4	11.6	12.2	14.7	9.2	25.5
Payment made grater than minimum payment due	55.9	52.5	60.3	61.8	36.6	37.2	61.9	60.8	31.0	53.0	59.7	50.5	61.6	52.4	58.9	56.2	55.3
Payment made equal to minimum payment due	26.0	32.3	17.9	21.3	41.5	51.2	17.9	25.7	27.6	35.0	14.3	29.7	22.1	31.7	21.1	33.1	6.4
Unable to pay at least minimum	4.5	3.0	6.4	3.7	7.3	2.3	5.2	3.4	10.3	2.0	7.8	4.4	4.7	3.7	5.3	1.5	12.8
Total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Table 10: Summarized results - stepwise regression analysis

Variable	β	R ² (adjusted)	ΔR^2
Consumer awareness of credit cards			
F1: Personal financial literacy			
Debt ceiling	.327***	.102	
F2: complementary/competitive credit card systems			
Marital status	.230***	.047	
F3: Credit risk			
Model 1: Income	.251***	.057	
Model 2: Income	.316***	.074	.023*
Debt ceiling	-.165*		
F4: Alternative forms of credit			
The highest level of education	.167*	.022	
Reasons for obtaining credit cards			
F1: Transactions convenience			
Model 1: Debt ceiling	.323***	.099	
Model 2: Debt ceiling	.359***	.121	.027*
The length of credit card ownership	-.168*		
F3: Marketing & communication programmes			
Model 1: Debt ceiling	-.254**	.054	
Model 2: Debt ceiling	-.213	.070	.021*
The length of credit card ownership	-.150		
F4: Short-term financial support			
Model 1: The length of credit card ownership	.245**	.054	
Model 2: The length of credit card ownership	.244**	.079	.030*
Gender	-.173*		
Consumer attitudes towards lifestyle outcomes of credit card usage			
F1: Indebtedness			
Debt ceiling	-.263***	.064	
F2: Access to mainstream society			
Model 1: Gender	-.354***	.120	
Model 2: Gender	-.337***	.141	.025*
Monthly income	.160*		
Model 3: Gender	-.285***	.177	.041**
Monthly income	.258**		
Debt ceiling	-.228**		
F4: Facilitated commerce			
Marital status	.160*	.020	
F5: Financial confidence			
Gender	.173**	.059	

Consumer attitudes towards governmental intervention			
Model 1: Debt ceiling	.262***	.063	
Model 2: Debt ceiling	.332***	.084	.026*
Monthly income	-.175*		

Notes:

* p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001.

Appendix

Appendix 1: Income and expenditure data

	1995/96	2002	2005	2006/07
Mean household income per month (Rs. †)	6476	128.3	20048	26286
Median household income per month (Rs.)	3793	8482	13617	16735
Gini coefficient of household income	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.49
Household size (No.)	4.5	4.2	4.1	4.1
Number of income earners per household	1.8	1.8	1.9	1.8
Mean income earners income per month (Rs.)	3367	6959	10563	14457
Gini coefficient of income earners income (Rs.)	0.52	0.53	0.55	0.55
Monetary income per month per household (Rs.)	5264	10386	17089	22616
Non-monetary income per month per household (Rs.)	1212	2419	2959	3671
Mean household expenditure per month (Rs.)	6525	13147	19151	22952
Expenditure on food and drink (Rs.)	3552	5848	7593	8641
Expenditure on non food and drink (Rs.)	2753	6993	11079	14311
Expenditure on liquor and tobacco (Rs.)	219	3.6	479	492
Food ratio (percentage)	54.4	44.5	39.6	37.6

Notes:

† 1 US \$ = 108 Sri Lankan Rupees (as at 30th September 2008)

Source: Department of Census and Statistics (www.statistics.gov.lk)